

INCOMPARABLE ENDURANCE: A POIGNANT ALLEGORY OF THE UNWAVERING COURAGE OF BATTERED WOMEN WHO PERSISTED IN ABUSIVE RELATIONSHIPS

¹MARY GERCEL P. GUAZA, ²GERMAN B. GUAZA, PhD, RCrim,
³Geraldine D. Rodriguez, EdD, PhD

Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges

Graduate School

General Santos City, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8224758>

Published Date: 08-August-2023

Abstract: The purpose of this study was to describe the experiences of battered women who remained in an abusive relationship. Phenomenological approach under qualitative research was employed in this study with ten (10) participants from Region XII. Additionally, an in depth interview and focus group discussion were conducted to gather the data. The results of the interview were transcribed, translated and coded to produce themes. As regards the experiences, the following were the themes: stayed because of children, feeling ashamed, deprived with rights, no choice, still hopeful and embrace the reality. Looking upon their challenges, the following themes were created: being mentally abused. Threats, emotionally depressed, dependent to husband, low morale, about to lose hope and self-blaming. As to their coping mechanism, the following themes were: being courageous, keep being patient, talking to partner, making oneself busy and self-motivation. As to their hopes and aspirations, the following themes were generated: think wisely, deal with partner carefully, women should be respected, hope for the better, be brave enough, protect your rights and help other battered women. This study lies in its potential to inform interventions and policies that can help prevent and address intimate partner violence, a pervasive global issue affecting millions of women around the world.

Keywords: Incomparable endurance, battered women, abusive relationship, phenomenology, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several women have become victims of being battered and other forms of abuse, but many of these cases remain unreported and unresolved. Battering is the recurrent use of physical and sexual aggression through force on a person closely associated with it. Similarly, wife beating refers to violent acts that are psychological, sexual, and physical by a husband to instill control of one's wife through fear and pain (Enaikele & Adeoye, 2022).

Moreover, many battered women develop a trauma bond with their abusers, leading to feelings of attachment and dependency. This bond can make it difficult for women to leave the relationship, as they may fear retaliation, lack financial resources, or worry about losing custody of their children. Additionally, cultural or religious beliefs, social isolation, and fear of judgment from others can contribute to women staying in abusive relationships. The effects of abuse on mental health can also explain why some women stay in abusive relationships. Prolonged exposure to abuse can lead to depression,

anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). These mental health issues can diminish a woman's self-esteem, increase her sense of helplessness, and cloud her judgment, making it difficult for her to leave the abusive relationship (Tullio et al., 2021).

Furthermore, the recurrence of this domestic violence is usually caused by the victims' silence. Battered women keep their silence because they are usually held responsible for and stigmatized over their condition. Wife battering is a prevalent case in Asian countries. For example, the Department of Social Welfare and Development in the Philippines 2012 reported that one out of five women aged 15-49, or 14.40 percent of married women, suffered physical abuse from their husbands; one in ten women experienced sexual violence. That year, 12 948 cases of abuse against women were recorded (Gyamerah et al., 2021).

Although laws like the Anti-Violence Against Women and Their Children Act of 2004 (R.A. 9262) exist to protect women in the Philippines, physical violence remains the most prevalent form of abuse suffered by married women. However, such laws empower the government to intervene in domestic affairs when acts of aggression are committed against women and children, providing hope for those victimized by such heinous acts (Balahadia & Astoveza, 2021).

Besides, Intimate partner violence (IPV) is a grave human rights violation and a pressing public health concern that affects individuals worldwide. Despite current indexing practices, data shows that violent crimes committed against intimate partners, such as spouses, boyfriends, and girlfriends, are predominantly committed against women, with non-lethal (rape, assault) and lethal (homicide) forms being common. However, it is essential to note that abusive behavior can manifest in ways beyond physical violence. Emotional or psychological abuse, which is often less researched and less visible, involves non-physical behaviors and attitudes that seek to control, subdue, punish, or isolate another person through the use of fear and humiliation (Balahadia et al., 2021).

Also, emotional abuse takes many forms, including verbal assault, dominance, control, isolation, ridicule, and using intimate knowledge for degradation. It is a calculated attack on the victim's emotional and psychological well-being and often serves as a prelude to physical abuse. Research has shown a correlation between physical and emotional abuse in batterer populations, with verbal abuse at the onset of a relationship being a significant predictor of subsequent physical spousal abuse (Letourneau et al., 2021; Radell et al., 2021).

Thus, there is an emerging emphasis on understanding emotional abuse as a construct separate from physical abuse, worthy of its theories and prevention strategies. Gender and age are pertinent to the burgeoning study of emotional abuse. Research on relationship violence has traditionally focused on youth and women of childbearing age as the prototypical victims, but there is now evidence thwarting this conventional view. For instance, men can be victims of IPV, and older women can be victims of relationship violence (Matheson et al., 2015).

For this reason, the study will be offered, for I want to speak from the experiences and stories of women who remain in abusive relationships. This study is to discover these experiences and how they affect them physically, mentally, and emotionally. I also want to find out if any key things have been effective in helping them continue their relationship without being abused. This study aims to be additional support to the development of the programs of the Philippine National Police Women Desk in General Santos City on the approach to these women.

Research on battered women who remain in abusive relationships is a critical and urgent area of study that requires attention from scholars, policymakers, and practitioners alike. Intimate partner violence (IPV) has devastating effects on women's physical and psychological well-being is well documented in the literature. However, researchers suggest that many women continue to stay in abusive relationships despite the risks and harms they face. This phenomenon requires thorough investigation to understand the complex dynamics contributing to women's decision-making processes and experiences of staying in abusive relationships. Further research in this area can help inform intervention strategies, policy development, and support services for battered women and ultimately contribute to preventing domestic violence and protecting survivors.

Purpose of the Study

The study aimed to investigate the complex and challenging experiences of women who continue to stay in abusive relationships. This study aimed to understand the reasons behind women's decisions to remain in such relationships despite the physical, emotional, and psychological harm they may be enduring. By delving into the experiences of battered women and uncovering the underlying factors that keep them from leaving their abusers, this study seeks to raise awareness about the importance of providing practical support and intervention for women trapped in abusive relationships. Ultimately, the

goal is to empower these women to be free from the cycle of abuse and to live safe and fulfilling lives free from violence and fear.

Research Question

1. What are the experiences of battered women who remained in abusive relationships?
2. What are the challenges they have experienced as battered women, and how did they cope with those challenges?
3. What are the hopes and aspirations of battered women, and what insights can they share with other women who have the same struggles?

Theoretical Lens

One possible theory for understanding why some battered women stay with their abusive partners despite the harm they experience is the theory of learned helplessness, proposed by Martin Seligman in 1975. According to this theory, individuals who have repeatedly faced uncontrollable adverse events,

such as abuse, may develop a belief that they are helpless and have no control over their situation. This learned helplessness can lead to a passive and resigned mindset, where individuals feel powerless to change their circumstances, even when opportunities for escape or intervention are available (Campbell, 2021).

Also, research by Walker (1979) on battered women found that many reported feeling trapped in abusive relationships due to a perceived lack of options and resources for leaving. They may fear retaliation from their abuser, worry about the safety of their children, or face financial and logistical challenges in finding alternative housing and support networks. This sense of helplessness may reinforce their decision to stay in the abusive relationship, as they may believe that leaving would not improve their situation.

Furthermore, the cycle of abuse, characterized by periods of tension building, the explosion of abuse, and honeymoon phases, can create a cycle of hope and despair for the victim (Walker, 1979). During the honeymoon phase, the abuser may apologize, show remorse, and promise to change, leading the victim to believe the relationship can be salvaged. This intermittent reinforcement of positive experiences in the relationship can make it difficult for the victim to leave, as they may cling to the hope of a better future with their abuser, despite the reality of ongoing abuse.

Moreover, cognitive dissonance, a theory proposed by Leon Festinger (1957), may also explain why some battered women remain in abusive relationships. Cognitive dissonance is the psychological discomfort arising when individuals hold conflicting beliefs or attitudes. In the case of battered women, they may experience dissonance between their belief in the abuser's positive qualities or the initial love they felt for their partner and the reality of the abusive behavior they are experiencing. To reduce this dissonance, they may engage in cognitive processes such as rationalization, denial, or minimization to justify staying in the relationship and avoid confronting the painful truth of the abuse.

In conclusion, the theory of learned helplessness, the cycle of abuse, and cognitive dissonance may explain why some battered women choose to remain in an abusive relationship. The perception of limited options, the hope of change, and the psychological discomfort of confronting the reality of abuse may contribute to their decision to stay, despite the harm they experience. It is essential to consider the complex psychological dynamics in abusive relationships when providing support and intervention for battered women and to offer comprehensive resources and strategies to empower them to break free from the cycle of violence.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This part presented related studies conducted by researchers in the same field. It also discussed the information and ideas that provided support to the said study.

Abusive Relationship

The mounting evidence from numerous studies serves as a grave reminder of Intimate Partner Violence (IPV)'s devastating impact on women's physical and mental well-being. Additionally, to end Violence Against Women (VAW) in the Philippines began in 1986, but the laws to protect Filipino women were not enacted until the 1990s. The most significant of these is the Republic Act No. [R.A.] 9262, which not only provides protection from all forms of abuse but also defines a crime against women by their partners as a public crime (Hailes, 2023; Subiani, 2023; Woerner et al, 2023).

Although violence against women has been invisible and socially acceptable for centuries, it has become a front-line problem in most countries. This has prompted procedural systems to adapt and incorporate recommendations from international human rights organizations into their respective legislations. Gender and development issues also need to be addressed by looking at the relations between women and men, social, political, and economic inequalities, and issues of power that hinder participation and opportunities for involvement in one's community. Violence against women is a shameful human rights violation without boundaries of geography, culture, or wealth. Until we end it, we cannot claim to have made real progress toward equality, development, and peace (Christensen, 2022).

Battered Women

Battered Woman's Syndrome (BWS) is a condition where victims of domestic violence are unable to place the responsibility for the abuse on their abusers, believe that the violence is their fault, fear for their lives and their children's, and hold an irrational belief that their abusers are all-knowing and omnipresent. Despite increasing awareness of the issue and enacting laws to protect women from domestic violence, it remains a prevalent problem in the Philippines (Zepinic, 2021; Zepinic, 2023; Nigam, 2016).

In addition, the result of choosing to stay in an abusive relationship is severe, resulting in loss of self, opportunities for a better life, peace of mind, psychological well-being, and love for one's partner. In contrast, leaving an abusive relationship allows women to regain their sense of self, inner strength, freedom, and hope. Studies have also shown that domestic violence can lead to long-term health problems, including chronic pain, physical disability, alcohol abuse, and depression. Coping mechanisms are identified as a factor in reducing adverse psychological outcomes for abuse victims. Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the psychological well-being of battered women, their coping mechanisms, and the relationship between the two (Vakil, 2020; Upadhyay, 2020; Deb, 2021).

Intimate Partner Violence (IPV)

Intimate Partner Violence is a pressing issue worldwide, causing harm and adverse outcomes for those affected. The WHO defines IPV as harmful behavior within an intimate relationship, including physical aggression, sexual coercion, psychological abuse, and controlling behaviors. IPV is one of the most common types of violence against women because men are more likely to hurt women than others. Research has found that male batterers often have aggressive dispositions and stress-related behaviors as their motivations. Abuse victims suffer physical injuries, emotional trauma, and medical conditions and may feel helpless and hopeless (Webster et al., 2021; Rebber et al., 2021).

However, they can seek help from family, friends, formal helpers, and legal counsel. While Walker's theory suggests that women are more docile and responsive to abuse, several studies have found that IPV is symmetrical, with both men and women committing violent acts. Women are more likely to use or commit violence and report physically assaulting their partners more frequently than men. Nonetheless, IPV remains a global issue that requires attention and intervention to support those impacted and prevent further harm (Meyer et al., 2020; Murphy et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2020).

Physical Abuse

Intimate partner violence often includes not only physical abuse but also psychological and sexual abuse, with the latter two having a severe impact on women's mental health, sometimes even more so than physical abuse. Unfortunately, psychological abuse is often overlooked as it frequently occurs alongside physical violence. However, there is not enough study on how economic abuse affects mental health. This study addresses that gap by examining the unique effects of different types of abuse (physical, psychological, or economic) on maternal mental health outcomes, such as psychological distress and suicide attempts, using self-reported data from a sample of women. By shedding light on the distinct consequences of different forms of abuse, this study can provide valuable insights into improving support for women facing intimate partner violence (Dickerson-Amaya & Coston, 2019).

VAWC Law – RA 9262

The State affirms its commitment to uphold the dignity of women and children and guarantee their complete protection of human rights. It recognizes the importance of safeguarding the family, particularly women, and children, from violence or danger. The State of the Philippines has committed to the Constitution and other international human rights agreements that it has ratified to protect women and children from experiencing violence (Macalalad, 2020; Tura, 2018; Realin, 2019).

Additionally, the Philippines revealed that various factors, such as family, economic, social, socio-cultural, and socio-political, contribute to violence against women in different contexts. Furthermore, the Philippine Statistics Authority's data

in 2004 showed that partnered women aged 15-49 experienced intimate partner physical and sexual violence. Another study conducted in Palawan found that homemakers were moderately aware of the provisions of RA 9262 but had a high perception of violence against women (Shah & Jacob, 2023).

Battering

Many women on welfare are plagued by poverty and abuse, with devastating consequences. Poverty brings about hardships such as homelessness and hunger and traps women in abusive relationships, leading to physical harm, diminished education, low self-esteem, missed opportunities, and limited employment prospects. As a result, policy and practice in workplaces, welfare offices, job training, placement programs, shelters for the homeless and battered women, and feminist and anti-poverty advocacy movements must recognize the links between work, battering, and poverty. The legal system must also be involved, as battering is against the law, and most jurisdictions offer remedies such as protective orders (Nelson, 2021; Martins, 2020).

Overall, the study and literature review highlight the need for comprehensive policies and support systems that address the complex and multifaceted issues battered women face. This includes policies that provide resources for women to escape abusive relationships and recover from the long-term effects of battering and policies that address the intersectionality of poverty, battering, and welfare reform. Additionally, it is necessary to increase awareness and understanding of the emotional and cognitive barriers battered women face in educational and vocational settings and the need for tailored support and accommodations to help them succeed.

3. METHOD

This chapter presented the methodology, which includes the research design, the role of the researcher, informants of the study, the method of data collection, data analysis and interpretation, trustworthiness, credibility, and ethical consideration.

Research Design

I used the qualitative phenomenological design under qualitative research since it described the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of battered women who remained in an abusive relationship in General Santos City. Qualitative research is a research method that aims to gather and interpret non-numerical data in order to gain insights and understanding. Unlike quantitative research, which focuses on collecting numerical data and often involves manipulating variables, qualitative research delves into real-world issues and provides a deeper understanding of them. By exploring experiences, perceptions, and behaviors of participants, qualitative research aims to address questions concerning the reasons and motivations behind phenomena, rather than simply quantifying them. One of the key strengths of qualitative research lies in its ability to generate hypotheses and support further investigation into quantitative data. This approach allows researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of a subject by examining the 'how' and 'why' aspects of a phenomenon. Through methods such as interviews, observations, and analysis of textual or audiovisual materials, researchers can explore the rich nuances, contexts, and complexities that quantitative measures may fail to capture. By collecting qualitative data, researchers can develop a holistic understanding of the subject matter, leading to a more comprehensive analysis and potential insights into social, psychological, or cultural factors that influence behaviors or perceptions (Ozuem et al., 2022; Hennink & Kaiser, 2022; Johnson et al., 2020).

Phenomenology seeks to describe the essential lived experiences. For the very nature of a phenomenon, this makes something that it is. As a research method, it is the study of essences. The essence of a phenomenon is universal, which can be described through a study of the structure that governs the instances or particular manifestations or the essence of that phenomenon (Van Manen, 1990).

Research Participants

This study focused on battered women subjected to abusive relationships in General Santos City. Seven participants were chosen for in-depth interviews, and seven were selected for focus group discussions, although only three were available for the latter. As van Manen (2014) suggested, phenomenological research prioritizes a deep exploration of individual experiences and often involves small sample sizes. Similarly, Morgan (1998) noted that focus group discussions typically require fewer participants than other research methods. Therefore, the small sample size of three participants for the focus group discussion in this study can still yield valuable insights into the participants' lived experiences. This approach aligns with the aim of phenomenological research, which is to capture the richness and depth of individual experiences rather than seeking generalizability or statistical significance.

In this study, specific inclusion criteria were established to ensure the selection of participants who met the requirements of the research objectives. A total of fourteen participants were chosen, with seven participants selected for in-depth interviews and another seven participants selected for focus group discussions. The primary criterion for inclusion was that all the women participants must have experienced some form of abuse from their partners or have been in an abusive relationship. This criterion was crucial to gather meaningful insights and perspectives on the experiences of individuals who have encountered domestic abuse. By including participants who had direct experiences with abuse, the study aimed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon and its impact on victims.

Data Collection

I used in-depth interviews and focus group discussions to gather data, ensuring participants were informed and available during the scheduled time and place. Qualitative data collection methods require understanding the underlying processes and changes in people's perceptions, and it is crucial to explain the research's nature and purpose to obtain permission from participants (Patton, 2015; Smith & Andrews, 1989; Willis, 2007).

Establishing positive relationships and rapport among participants is essential for the study's success. To gain access, I sought permission from the Police Superintendent through formal request letters. Then I made a personal appearance to introduce myself and state my purpose, assuring confidentiality to protect participants' identities (Mack et al., 2005).

During meetings with participants, I ensured that everyone agreed to be accompanied by someone to take notes and that the collected data would be evaluated constructively with the participants to increase its reliability. Information confirmed by multiple individuals was presumed to be accurate. Overall, this study prioritized building trust with participants, maintaining confidentiality, and ensuring that the data collected accurately reflected their experiences.

Data Analysis Procedures

Thematic analysis was utilized in this study to analyze the collected data. The goal was to detect any recurring patterns that represented the concepts the participants conveyed during the data collection process. The data was classified into coherent categories that synthesized and provided meaning to the notes. Specific codes were created to assist in sorting the responses into the categories above and identifying emerging themes. Thorne (2000) stated that data analysis is the most intricate and enigmatic of all the phases of a qualitative project and receives the least amount of thoughtful discussion in the literature.

Thematic analysis entails recognizing and describing implicit and explicit ideas within the data, which constitute the themes. Mack et al. (2005) added that thematic analysis is the most popular method of analysis in qualitative research. The steps in the thematic analysis include familiarizing oneself with the data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing the themes, defining and naming the themes, and constructing the report, as outlined by Boyatzis (1998). Thematic analysis is a technique for analyzing and reporting on the pattern of themes in the data (Boyatzis, 1998; Roulston, 2001). Thematic analysis is adaptable, and what researchers do with the themes after discovering them varies based on the research's objectives and analysis process.

4. RESULTS

This chapter presented the experiences of the study participants, their abilities to see the inner nature and ideas that emerged from the information gathered from in-depth interviews and focus group discussions.

The following research questions made it possible to produce data from the informants: What are the lived experiences of battered women who remained in abusive relationships? What challenges have they experienced as battered women, and how did they cope? What are the hopes and aspirations of battered women, and what insights can they share with other women who have the same struggles?

Table 1. The Experiences of Battered Women Who Remained in an Abusive Relationship

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
She stayed because of her children's safety Leaving when kids grow up Waited for the children to mature Battered rather than leaving children She chose because of her children	Stayed because of Children

<p>Ashamed of being criticize Insulted in front of children and neighbor Be shouted at for no reason Rebuked by husbands in front of kids In a drunken husband's box Not wanting anyone to know she is battered</p>	<p>Feeling Ashamed</p>
<p>Not allowed to use her own cellphone Being order to buy alcoholic drink Feeling hurt and disappointed Wish to just stay away from him if she could Very jealous and deprived to even talk to friends Just stayed due to poverty</p>	<p>Deprived with Rights</p>
<p>Cannot do anything The husband is the provider of the family Choose to remain silent just to avoid trouble Do not have anywhere to go Use strength to just go on just for family's sake Believed that everything will be okay someday Imagined that the husband fears losing her. Will just look for a better one</p>	<p>No Choice</p>
<p>If given a chance, she still wants to have better She still wants to have a better life Still hopeful for the husband to change Hopeful that her family will retaliate if she got abused Use strength to just go on just for family's sake Believed that everything will be okay someday Imagined that the husband fears losing her. Will just look for a better one Hope not to get battered anymore Hoping to change his behavior</p>	<p>Still Hopeful</p>
<p>Choose to just remain and respect what they have Just letting her husband to hurt her Accept being battered as long as he do his obligation</p>	<p>Embraced the Reality</p>

Stayed Because of Children

In this theme, battered women choose to remain in an abusive relationship because they believe it is in the best interest of their children's safety. These women may fear that leaving their abusive partner could result in harm to their children or themselves. Their primary concern is to protect their children from witnessing or experiencing the violence firsthand.

Feeling Ashamed

Battered women who remain in abusive relationships often experience feelings of shame. This can stem from societal stigmatization or a belief that they have somehow failed to maintain a healthy relationship. They may internalize the blame for the abuse, feeling embarrassed or humiliated about their situation.

Deprived with Rights

Women in abusive relationships may find themselves deprived of their basic human rights. This can include the right to physical and emotional safety, the right to make decisions freely, and the right to live without fear. Abusers often exert control over their victims, restricting their freedom and autonomy.

No Choice

Many battered women feel trapped in their abusive relationships due to a perceived lack of options. They may believe that leaving the relationship would jeopardize their safety or result in even worse consequences. Factors such as financial dependence, fear of retaliation, or limited support networks can contribute to a sense of helplessness and a belief that they have no choice.

Still Hopeful

Despite enduring ongoing abuse, some women in abusive relationships hold onto a glimmer of hope. They may believe that their partner will change or that the relationship can be salvaged. This hope, although sometimes unfounded, can provide a sense of comfort or serve as a coping mechanism in a challenging situation.

Embrace the reality

Over time, some battered women come to accept the reality of their situation. They acknowledge that their relationship is abusive and recognize the negative impact it has on themselves and their children. This acceptance can be a crucial step towards seeking help and eventually leaving the abusive relationship.

Table 2. The Challenges and Coping Mechanisms of the Battered Women Who Remained in an Abusive Relationship

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
I. Challenges	
Keep on thinking about how she was battered Felt being tortured mentally Mentally and physically affected Overthink of what might happen	Being Mentally Abused
He said he will inflict her She will be in danger if she won't follow his command Threatened whenever she talks to friends	Threats
Felt very lonely Cannot sleep very well because of being hurt Overthinking about things that happened and end up being so depressed	Emotionally Depressed
Dependent on money matters Cannot sustain her own needs Afraid to lose food supply if she ran away Just stay because of being too dependent to her husband Felt low moral	Dependent to Husband Low Moral
Rights were violated Tried to be put inside the box in front of their children Being beaten without mercy	
Thinking of giving up No hope anymore Felt very tired with the relationship Telling oneself to just give-up everything	About to Lose Hope
Blamed oneself Nagging oneself Told oneself to be just nothing Told oneself to just give-up	Self-Blaming
II. Coping Mechanisms	
Bravely face and overcome the problems and difficulties Controlling the emotion Staying strong to every challenge Accepting the fact that he will leave Making oneself brave in facing difficulties Keep on being strong in facing reality	Being Courageous

Never be afraid to leave	
Keep on being patient Just doing her obligations mindlessly	Being Patient
Finding time to talk to her partner Striving hard to please her partner Showing honesty all the time	Talking to Partner
Busy doing the responsibilities in the house Working hard Use social media and avoid going outside Keep on doing activities Not minding his words whenever he got drunk	Making Oneself Busy
Just pray and boost oneself Keep oneself strong Think for a positive change of behavior Just keep being calm and strong She does not allow problems to defeat her Make oneself become more strong Aimed for a much better relationship	About to Lose Hope

I. Challenges

Being Mentally Abused

The challenge faced by battered women who remain in abusive relationships includes being subjected to constant mental abuse and threats. These women often experience psychological manipulation, intimidation, and constant fear for their safety. The abuser may use various tactics such as verbal threats, controlling behaviors, and emotional manipulation to maintain power and control over the victim.

Threats

Threats create an atmosphere of fear and intimidation, making it extremely difficult for battered women to escape an abusive relationship. The constant fear of reprisals, physical harm, or even death may restrict their ability to seek help or reach out for support.

Emotionally Depressed

Living in an abusive relationship can lead to severe emotional depression for battered women. They often feel trapped, helpless, and overwhelmed by the constant abuse they endure. The emotional turmoil and constant stress can lead to feelings of sadness, anxiety, and hopelessness. The constant degradation and negativity from the abuser can take a toll on their mental well-being and self-esteem.

Dependent to Husband

Another significant challenge faced by battered women is dependency on their abusive partners. This dependence can be financial, emotional, or even social. Many women in abusive relationships may rely on their partners for financial support or fear the consequences of leaving, such as losing custody of children. They might also feel isolated from friends and family due to the abuser's control, further increasing dependency.

Low Moral

Living in an abusive relationship can cause battered women to experience low self-esteem and a diminished sense of self-worth. The constant belittlement, insults, and devaluation by the abuser can erode their confidence and leave them feeling unworthy of love and respect. The abuser often manipulates their self-perception, making them believe they are to blame for the abuse, further lowering their morale.

About to Lose Hope

Battered women who remain in abusive relationships often find themselves on the brink of losing hope. The cycle of abuse, false promises of change, and intermittent apologies can create a sense of confusion and make it difficult for them to see a way out. They may blame themselves for the abuse, believing they deserve it or that they can't escape the situation. This self-blaming mindset can reinforce feelings of hopelessness and prevent them from seeking help.

Self-Blaming

In the context of battered women who remain in abusive relationships, self-blaming refers to the tendency of these women to hold themselves responsible for the abuse they endure. They may believe that they somehow caused or provoked the abuse, leading to feelings of guilt and shame. Self-blaming can be a significant challenge for these women as it can hinder their ability to seek help or leave the abusive relationship.

II. Coping Mechanisms

Be Courageous

Battered women who choose to remain in an abusive relationship often display remarkable courage in navigating their circumstances. This coping mechanism involves summoning strength, resilience, and determination to persist in difficult situations. They may develop a strong internal conviction that allows them to withstand the abuse and continue to navigate daily life, inspiring hope for a better future.

Keep Being Patient

Patience becomes an essential coping mechanism for battered women as they endure the challenges of an abusive relationship. Despite the hardships, they may choose to patiently wait for conditions to improve or for an opportunity to escape safely. This coping mechanism requires immense emotional strength and self-control, allowing them to bide their time until they feel ready to take action.

Talking to Partner

Some battered women resort to communication as a coping mechanism, believing that open dialogue with their abusive partners may lead to positive changes. They may engage in conversations to express their concerns, boundaries, and the impacts of the abuse, hoping that it will initiate a shift in behavior. However, it is important to acknowledge that this coping mechanism may not always yield the desired results and can potentially exacerbate the abuse.

Making Oneself Busy

Battered women often find solace in keeping themselves occupied with tasks or activities. By focusing on external engagements such as work, hobbies, or caring for children, they can temporarily alleviate the emotional and psychological distress caused by the abuse. This coping mechanism provides a means of escape and can also serve as a distraction from their circumstances, allowing them to find moments of respite or a sense of empowerment.

Self-Motivation

In the face of ongoing abuse, it is not uncommon for battered women to experience moments where they feel like they are losing hope. This coping mechanism involves recognizing and acknowledging their emotions of despair, sadness, or frustration, but also mustering the strength to persevere. While it may seem challenging, seeking support from friends, family, or professionals and engaging in self-care activities can help restore hope and create a path towards eventual healing and liberation.

Table 3. The Hopes, Aspirations, and Insights of Battered Women Who Remained in an Abusive Relationship

Cluster Themes	Emergent Themes
Hopes	
Hoping companionship will continue smoothly Believe that you can survive Thinking that efforts will be paid off someday	Hope for the Better

Aspirations	
Thinking that you will become successful Don't lose hope and strive to help other victim Show that you have dignity Remain being true to yourself Do your obligation as a wife	Women should be Respected
Insights	
Think the advantage and disadvantage very well Women have the right freedom to find justice Have the courage to stay strong Be careful and protect yourself Fight for yourself Don't allow yourself to get battered Be submissive but brave Show to your husband that you have equal rights	Protect your Rights
Share tips on how to deal with partner Let other women know that wives are protected Be willing to listen to other victims' testimony Show everyone that you can do it	Help other Battered Women

I. Hopes

Hope for the Better

The participants despite being emotionally depressed mentally abused and experienced threats still hoping and optimistic with a feeling of confidence for a bright future to happen.

II. Aspirations

Women should be Respected

Women in this study accepted difficulties in their real life but they were compelled to take steps toward a safer future by embracing the reality, initiating themselves to achieve the fulfillment of their aspirations to be respected by partners in the long run. Maintain my role as a good wife for him. Showing him that I'm a human being needs to be respected with dignity.

III. Insights

Be Brave Enough

This theme emphasizes the importance of courage and inner strength for battered women who choose to remain in an abusive relationship. It recognizes that leaving an abusive partner is not always a straightforward decision and requires immense bravery. It encourages these women to tap into their personal resilience, gather their courage, and take steps towards empowering themselves.

Protect Your Rights

This theme emphasizes the importance of empowering battered women to stand up for their rights. It encourages them to find the strength within themselves to break free from the cycle of abuse and take action to ensure their safety and well-being. It stresses the need to build self-confidence, seek legal protection, and connect with support organizations that can guide them through the process of reclaiming their rights. By being brave and assertive, battered women can reclaim their autonomy, regain control over their lives, and build a future free from violence.

Help Other Battered Women

This theme highlights the significance of creating a sense of sisterhood and solidarity among battered women. It emphasizes the importance of reaching out to others who have experienced similar abuse and offering support, understanding, and empathy. By sharing experiences, offering resources, and creating safe spaces for discussion, women can help each other heal, regain their self-worth, and recognize that they are not alone in their struggles. Empowering other battered women involves providing emotional support, practical guidance, and encouraging them to seek professional help, ultimately fostering a community that champions healing, growth, and resilience.

5. DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the study's findings, highlighting the comparison to other existing research, its practical applications, implications for future research, and concluding remarks. They explored the lived experiences of battered women, including the reasons for staying in abusive relationships. The study collected valuable insights into the participants' experiences during abuse through in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The study's results could serve as a valuable resource for future researchers and other women, helping them gain a deeper understanding of the challenges battered women face and the trauma they endure at the hands of their abusers. Furthermore, the findings may inform the development of programs and policies to protect and empower women, ensuring they get the support and tools they require to speak up and take back control of their life.

Implications to Practice

Based on the findings, the following implications for practice are offered.

Six major themes were generated in the experiences of the Battered Women Who Remained in an Abusive Relationship: Staying Because of Children, Feeling Ashamed, Deprived of Rights, having No Choice, Still Hopeful, and Embracing reality

The Experiences of Battered Women Who Remained in an Abusive Relationship Stayed Because of Children

Battered women who remain in an abusive relationship because of their children may need specialized support that addresses their emotional, practical, and safety needs while prioritizing the well-being of both the women and their children. Providing comprehensive and trauma-informed support to battered women who stay in abusive relationships because of their children is essential. This should include Empowerment and Safety Planning: rather than being told what to do, battered women should make their own decisions and devise a strategy to keep themselves and their children safe. This may involve identifying safe spaces, creating a support network, and developing strategies to de-escalate dangerous situations.

Feeling Ashamed. Battered women who remain in an abusive relationship may experience feelings of shame due to societal, cultural, or internalized beliefs about domestic violence. It is crucial to address and challenge the shame experienced by battered women who remain in abusive relationships and to provide support that promotes self-compassion, empowerment, and resilience. This may include: Educating and Challenging Societal and Cultural Beliefs: Societal and cultural beliefs that blame or shame victims of domestic violence can contribute to a battered woman's feelings of shame. Educating individuals about domestic violence dynamics, challenging victim-blaming attitudes, and promoting empathy and understanding toward survivors is essential. This may involve community-based awareness campaigns, educational programs, and advocacy efforts to change societal and cultural norms.

Deprived of Rights. The experiences of battered women who remain in abusive relationships indicate a significant deprivation of their fundamental human rights. These women often face various forms of physical, emotional, psychological, and financial abuse, which can severely impact their physical and mental well-being. The implications of remaining in an abusive relationship may include decreased self-esteem, increased risk of injury or death, social isolation, and long-term trauma. It is imperative to prioritize the safety and well-being of battered women who choose to remain in abusive relationships. Ensure battered women access safe and confidential support services like hotlines, shelters, and counseling services. These services should provide a nonjudgmental and supportive environment for women to seek help without fear of reprisal.

No Choice. The experiences of battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite having no choice may be complex and multifaceted. These women may face various barriers, such as financial dependence, fear of retaliation, lack of social support, cultural or religious beliefs, or limited access to resources and services, which prevent them from leaving the abusive relationship. It is crucial to approach the issue of battered women who remain in abusive relationships with empathy and understanding, recognizing the complexity of their situation. Increase access to resources: Ensure battered women access comprehensive resources, such as shelters, legal assistance, counseling, and financial support, regardless of their socioeconomic status or background.

Still Hopeful. The experiences of battered women who remain in abusive relationships while maintaining a sense of hope may indicate the complexity of the dynamics of abuse. These women may hold onto hope for various reasons, such as love for their partner, cultural or religious beliefs, fear of change or the unknown, or a belief that the situation may improve. It is essential to address the concerns of battered women who remain hopeful in abusive relationships with sensitivity and

understanding. Provide nonjudgmental support: Offer unconditional and nonjudgmental listening to battered women who express hopefulness in abusive relationships. Avoid blaming or shaming them for their choices, and acknowledge their feelings and experiences with empathy and compassion.

Embrace Reality. Battered women who embrace the reality of their abusive relationships may have come to terms with the situation and may be ready to take steps toward change. This may indicate a shift in their mindset and a willingness to acknowledge the severity of the abuse and the need for intervention. It is critical to provide resources and encouragement to battered women who have accepted the reality of their abusive marriages. Help battered women cope with the devastating realization that they are in an abusive relationship by providing emotional support. One approach is to pay close attention, acknowledge their feelings, and praise their courage in facing the truth. Without passing judgment, reassure them that they are not to blame and that help is at hand.

On the Challenges of Battered Women Who Remained in an Abusive Relationship as to being Mentally Abused

The challenges of battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite experiencing mental abuse can significantly negatively impact their mental health and well-being. The effects of prolonged mental abuse, such as gaslighting, manipulation, and emotional control, can be long-lasting and pervasive, as well as post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Battered women who are mentally abused may also face challenges in recognizing the abuse, as it may not leave physical scars and may be normalized or rationalized by the abuser, leading to feelings of confusion, self-doubt, and guilt. Providing support and resources for battered women experiencing mental abuse in an abusive relationship is crucial. Raising awareness about the signs and effects of mental abuse, and providing education about healthy relationships and boundaries, can help battered women recognize and understand the dynamics of mental abuse. This can empower them to seek help and take steps toward leaving the abusive relationship.

Threats. The challenges faced by battered women who remain in abusive relationships, although threats, are complex and multifaceted. These women often experience fear, intimidation, manipulation, and a sense of powerlessness from their abusive partners. Battered women may face various barriers in leaving the abusive relationship, such as financial dependence, lack of social support, fear of retaliation, cultural or societal norms, and limited access to legal resources. Providing comprehensive support and resources to battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats is crucial. Creating safe and confidential spaces where battered women can seek help without fear of judgment or retaliation. This can be achieved through shelters, hotlines, or community organizations that offer support, counseling, and advocacy for survivors of domestic violence.

Emotionally Depressed. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats are at risk of experiencing emotional depression due to prolonged exposure to abuse. The constant stress, trauma, and manipulation from the abusive partner can lead to mental health challenges. The emotional impact of abuse can be severe and long-lasting, affecting a survivor's overall well-being and quality of life. Addressing the emotional well-being of battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats is critical. Providing access to mental health services, including counseling and therapy, to help battered women cope with the emotional impact of abuse. These services should be affordable, accessible, and tailored to the specific needs of survivors, taking into account cultural, linguistic, and other relevant considerations.

Dependent to Husband. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may become financially dependent on their abusive partners, which can further exacerbate their challenges. Economic abuse, such as controlling finances, withholding resources, and limiting employment opportunities, is often used by abusive partners to maintain power and control over their victims. This dependence on the abusive partner can create significant barriers for battered women to leave the relationship and seek safety. Addressing financial dependence is crucial to supporting battered women in abusive relationships. Empowering battered women to become financially independent by providing them with resources and tools for education, job training, and employment opportunities. This can include job placement services, vocational training programs, and financial literacy education to build their skills and confidence in managing their finances.

Low Moral. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may experience a decline in their morale or sense of self-worth. The repeated abuse, manipulation, and degradation from their abusive partners can harm their self-esteem, self-confidence, and morale. This can further perpetuate a cycle of abuse. Low self-esteem can make it harder for someone to leave an abusive partner, leading to feelings of hopelessness, helplessness, and the sense that they deserve the violence. In order to help battered women who continue to be in violent relationships, it is essential to address the issue of poor morale. Creating nonjudgmental environments where battered women can talk about their experiences and receive emotional support from others. Counseling, support groups, and peer-to-peer support programs that provide empathetic listening, acceptance, and motivation can all restore individuals' sense of worth and confidence.

About to lose hope. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may be at risk of losing hope due to the prolonged and repetitive nature of the abuse they experience. The constant fear, trauma, and manipulation from their abusive partners can wear down their resilience and optimism, leading to hopelessness and despair. This loss of hope can further trap them in an abusive relationship, as they may feel powerless and unable to envision a better future. Restoring hope is crucial in supporting battered women who remain in abusive relationships. Providing trauma-informed counseling and therapy to help battered women process their emotions, build resilience, and develop coping strategies to manage the impact of abuse. This can include cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT), mindfulness techniques, and other evidence-based approaches that address hopelessness's emotional and psychological aspects.

Self-blaming. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may engage in self-blaming behavior, taking responsibility for the abuse they experience. This can stem from the manipulation and gaslighting tactics used by their abusive partners to shift blame onto the victim, making them feel guilty or at fault for the abuse they endure. Self-blaming can further perpetuate the cycle of abuse, as it can lower the survivor's self-esteem. Addressing self-blaming behavior is crucial in supporting battered women in abusive relationships. Providing psychoeducation and raising awareness about the dynamics of abuse, including the tactics used by abusers to shift blame onto their victims. This can help survivors understand that they are not to blame for the abuse they experience and reduce self-blaming behavior.

On the Coping of Battered Women Who Remained in an Abusive Relationship as to Being Courageous

Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may employ courage as a coping mechanism to survive the abusive situation. These women may demonstrate immense courage in enduring the abuse, protecting their children, and navigating the complexities of an abusive relationship. However, this courage can also contribute to their continued stay in the abusive relationship, as they may feel that leaving would require even more courage, resources, and support, which they may not feel they possess. Recognizing and supporting the courage of battered women is crucial while also providing resources to help them move toward safety. Validating and acknowledging the immense courage that battered women exhibit in their daily lives. This can involve reinforcing positive affirmations about their resilience, strength, and bravery and acknowledging their challenges in leaving an abusive relationship.

Keep being patient. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may employ patience as a coping mechanism to navigate the abusive situation. These women may believe that if they wait long enough, the abuse will stop or the situation will improve, and they may hold on to hope that their partner will change. This patience may also stem from fear of further harm or retaliation if they take action to leave the abusive relationship. While patience can be a coping mechanism for some battered women, it is essential to recognize that prolonged patience may perpetuate the cycle of abuse. Providing education and information about the dynamics of abuse and the impact of long-term exposure to abuse. This can help battered women understand that patience alone may not lead to positive change and that taking action to seek help and safety is crucial.

Talking to partner. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may use a coping mechanism of talking to their abusive partner to manage the abuse. These women may attempt to reason with or communicate with their partner to de-escalate the abusive behavior, seek reconciliation, or try to understand and address the underlying issues contributing to the abuse. However, this coping mechanism may be ineffective, as abusive partners often use manipulation, control, and violence to maintain power and control, and talking may not lead to positive change in the abusive relationship. While communication and dialogue are essential in healthy relationships, it is crucial to recognize that talking to an abusive partner may not be effective in addressing the abuse. Providing education about the dynamics of abuse and the patterns of abusive behavior, including the fact that abusive partners may not be willing or able to change without professional intervention. This can help battered women understand that talking alone may not lead to positive change in an abusive relationship.

Making oneself busy. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may employ the coping mechanism of keeping themselves busy to distract themselves from the abusive situation. These women may engage in various activities, such as work, household chores, hobbies, or socializing, to escape from the distress and pain caused by the abuse. By keeping themselves busy, they may try to avoid facing the complex reality of their situation and use busyness as a form of emotional numbing or avoidance. Encouraging self-care and self-reflection: Battered women must prioritize their physical and emotional well-being. This can involve engaging in self-care activities, such as exercise, healthy eating, getting enough rest, and self-reflection through journaling, meditation, or therapy to process their emotions and experiences.

Self-Motivation. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships despite threats may employ self-motivation as a coping mechanism to keep themselves going in the face of adversity. These women may find inner strength and determination to survive and endure the abuse. They may use self-motivation to maintain hope and resilience amid a challenging and abusive situation. While self-motivation can be a powerful coping mechanism, it is essential to recognize that it may not be enough to sustain long-term well-being in an abusive relationship. Validating and reinforcing self-motivation: Battered women who exhibit self-motivation should be acknowledged for their strength and resilience. Encouraging and reinforcing their self-motivation can help boost their self-esteem and confidence and empower them to continue seeking support and taking steps toward safety and healing.

On the Hopes and Aspirations of Battered Women Who Remained in an Abusive Relationship as to Think Wisely

Battered women who remain in abusive relationships may still have hopes and aspirations but must think wisely about their situation to navigate their challenges. These women may have dreams and goals for their future. However, they may need to carefully consider their options and make strategic decisions to protect themselves and work towards a better future. Encouraging critical thinking: Battered women navigating an abusive relationship can benefit from critical thinking skills to carefully evaluate their situation, risks, and potential outcomes. Encouraging them to think critically about their circumstances, assess their options, and consider the potential consequences of their decisions can help them make informed choices.

Deal with your partner carefully. Battered women who choose to remain in an abusive relationship may face significant challenges in dealing with their partners carefully. This may happen because of apprehension, monetary reliance, cultural or societal pressures, low self-esteem, and a lack of support structures. Compassion and tolerance for battered women who stay in abusive situations are crucial. Instead of passing judgment or assigning blame, offering assistance while they carefully manage their position is essential. Raise awareness about the complexities of abusive relationships and the hardships endured by battered women who stay in them. Stigma and misinformation can be mitigated by implementing community-based programs, workshops, and awareness campaigns.

Women should be respected. The hopes and aspirations of battered women who remain in abusive relationships are often overlooked, and their rights to respect and safety are compromised. The health and safety of battered women must take precedence, and they must be given the means to exit abusive relationships. Promote education and awareness programs in communities, schools, and workplaces to educate individuals about the dynamics of abusive relationships, the rights of women, and the importance of respecting women's autonomy and agency.

I hope for the better. There are likely a variety of emotional and psychological factors at play when battered women choose to stay in an abusive relationship, including but not limited to fear, dependence, lack of resources, society and cultural norms, trauma bonding, and low self-esteem. There is a chance they are clinging to dreams of a brighter tomorrow. However, in an abusive relationship, they may encounter tremendous obstacles to reaching those goals. The health and safety of battered women in violent relationships must be top priorities. Practical assistance in locating resources, including crisis hotlines, shelters, counselors, lawyers, and social workers, should be provided, along with empathy, support, and nonjudgmental understanding. Building trust and rapport takes time, but it may be accomplished through encouraging open dialogue and attentive listening. Helping someone requires respecting their autonomy and choices while gently dispelling any myths or reasons they may have for continuing. If parents are educated about the dynamics of abuse and the numerous assistance options they should make for their families. Working with specialists from different fields, such as police, social workers, counselors, and lawyers, can provide a more comprehensive solution to their problems. Finally, a safer and more hopeful environment may be created for battered women who hope for a better future through raising social awareness, lobbying, and legislative changes to address the core causes of domestic violence and offer systemic support for survivors.

Have some guts. Battered women who stay in violent relationships may be unable to pursue their goals and dreams because of the relationship's danger and imbalance of power. Battered women may feel helpless, unsafe, and unable to leave an abusive relationship, which might hinder their capacity to pursue their dreams. Those battered women who stay in violent relationships out of fear must be given the tools they need to break free finally. Insight and Agency through Learning: Offer guidance and instruction on how to recognize abusive relationships, how to break the cycle of abuse, and where to find help. Facilitate women's decision-making by educating them about their rights, choices, and resources.

Protect your rights. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships may face challenges in protecting their rights due to the power dynamics and control exerted by their abusive partners. They may feel disempowered and struggle to assert their rights and pursue their hopes and aspirations. In order to safeguard abused women's rights in an abusive relationship,

offering them assistance and services is critical. Help battered women learn about their legal rights and options by providing them with legal representation and information. The topics covered could include their rights to a restraining order, child custody, and visitation. Help them navigate the legal system by connecting them with professionals who can advise them and advocates who can fight for them.

Help other Battered Women. Battered women who remain in abusive relationships may face challenges in achieving their hopes and aspirations due to the ongoing abuse and its negative impact on their mental, emotional, and physical well-being. The abuse, fear, and dependence cycle can create significant barriers to realizing their dreams and goals. It is essential to help battered women who choose to remain in abusive relationships, with the ultimate goal of empowering them to leave and live a safe and fulfilling life. Educate society about the complexities of abusive relationships and why some women may choose to stay. Challenge victim-blaming attitudes and promote understanding and empathy towards battered women's experiences.

Implication for Future Research

Longitudinal Studies: Future research should utilize longitudinal study designs to track battered women who remain in abusive relationships over an extended period. This would allow researchers to understand why some women stay in abusive relationships despite their risks and challenges and how their situations may change or evolve.

Intersectionality: Future research should adopt an intersectional approach that recognizes the unique experiences of battered women who belong to different marginalized groups, such as women of color, LGBTQ+ women, immigrant women, women with disabilities, etc. This would shed light on the complexities of their experiences and the unique barriers they may face in leaving abusive relationships.

Contextual Factors: Future research should investigate the contextual factors influencing battered women's decision to remain in an abusive relationship. This could include factors such as cultural norms, economic dependence, social support networks, access to resources and services, legal and policy frameworks, and other contextual factors that shape a woman's decision-making process in the context of abuse.

Mental Health and Trauma: Future research should explore the effects of trauma on battered women who remain in abusive relationships. This could include investigating the role of trauma bonding, Stockholm syndrome, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, anxiety, and other mental health factors that may impact a woman's decision to stay in an abusive relationship.

Intervention Strategies: Future research should focus on developing and evaluating innovative intervention strategies specifically designed to support and empower battered women who remain in abusive relationships. This could include exploring the effectiveness of trauma-informed care, culturally-tailored interventions, strengths-based approaches, and other interventions prioritizing the survivor's autonomy, safety, and well-being.

Survivor Voices: Future research should center on the voices and experiences of battered women in abusive relationships. Incorporating survivor perspectives in the research process would provide a more nuanced understanding of why some women stay in abusive relationships, the strategies they employ to cope, and their needs and preferences for support and intervention.

Prevention and Early Intervention: The underlying reasons for domestic violence must be addressed, and healthy relationships should be encouraged in future studies.

This could include exploring strategies such as community-based initiatives, education, awareness programs, policy changes, and other proactive approaches to reduce the incidence of domestic violence and support women in leaving abusive relationships before they become entrenched.

Future research on battered women who remain in abusive relationships should adopt a multi-dimensional and inclusive approach that considers the complex interplay of individual, interpersonal, societal, and systemic factors that influence women's decisions and experiences in the context of abuse. Understanding the characteristics of abusive relationships and creating successful measures to support and empower survivors requires addressing these research implications.

Concluding Remarks

In conclusion, the research on battered women who remained in abusive relationships sheds light on domestic violence's complex and multifaceted nature. It underscores the myriad reasons some women stay in abusive relationships, including

fear, economic dependence, social isolation, cultural and societal norms, trauma bonding, and psychological manipulation. It also highlights these women's barriers when attempting to leave, such as lack of resources, limited support systems, legal challenges, and societal stigmatization.

The research findings emphasize the importance of adopting a nuanced and victim-centered approach when addressing the issue of domestic violence, recognizing that leaving an abusive relationship is not always a straightforward or viable option for all battered women. It underscores the need for comprehensive and multi-disciplinary interventions that prioritize the safety and well-being of the survivor while addressing the systemic factors that contribute to the perpetuation of abuse.

In addition, the study emphasizes the need to remove the stigma associated with domestic violence survivors. It also stresses the importance of raising public awareness, educating the public, and enacting governmental changes to combat domestic abuse and hold offenders accountable.

In conclusion, the research on battered women who remained in an abusive relationship underscores the complexity and gravity of domestic violence and calls for a holistic and survivor-centered approach that recognizes and addresses the diverse and intersecting challenges faced by survivors of domestic violence who choose to stay. It is essential to work towards ending the cycle of abuse and providing a safer and more supportive environment for all survivors. This work must also focus on putting an end to the abuse itself.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ali, P. A., & Naylor, P. B. (2013). *Intimate partner violence: A narrative review of the feminist, social and ecological explanations for its causation*. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 18, 611–619. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2013.07.009>
- [2] Akhter, R., Wilson, J. K., Haque, S. E., & Ahamed, N. (2022). Like a caged bird: The coping strategies of economically empowered women who are victims of intimate partner violence in Bangladesh. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 37(11-12), NP9040-NP9065.
- [3] Akl, S., Temares, A. E., Diaz, B. N., & Walker, L. E. (2023). Psychological testing in forensic evaluations of battered women who kill. *Journal of Aggression, Maltreatment & Trauma*, 32(1-2), 148-166.
- [4] Alessandrino, F., Keraliya, A., Lebovic, J., Mitchell Dyer, G. S., Harris, M. B., Tornetta III, P., ... & Khurana, B. (2020). Intimate partner violence: a primer for radiologists to make the “invisible” visible. *Radiographics*, 40(7), 2080-2097.
- [5] Avanci, J. Q., Pinto, L. W., & Minayo, M. C. D. S. (2017). *Self-harm throughout all life cycles: profile of victims using urgent and emergency care services in Brazilian state capitals*. *Ciência & Saúde Coletiva*, 22, 2841-2850.
- [6] Bagwell-Gray, M. E., Messing, J. T., Durfee, A. A., & Spearman, K. J. (2023). A Critical Examination of the Influences of Intimate Partner Violence, Help- Seeking, and Social Identity on Women’s Experiences Seeking and Obtaining Civil Protection Orders. *Women & Criminal Justice*, 1-18.
- [7] Balahadia, F. F., & Astoveza, Z. J. M. (2021). *Analysis and Evaluation of Violence against Women and their Children Incident Report: Data Exploration*. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(1), 1-13.
- [8] Balahadia, F., Mortel, Z. J., Astoveza, N. E. A., & Jamolin, G. (2021). *Development and Implementation of Violence against Women and their Children Report System Mobile Application for the Province of Laguna*. *Southeast Asian Journal of Science and Technology*, 6(2 (SI)), 27-35.
- [9] Barrios, V. R., Khaw, L. B. L., Bermea, A., & Hardesty, J. L. (2021). *Future directions in intimate partner violence research: An intersectionality framework for analyzing women’s processes of leaving abusive relationships*. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 36(23-24), NP12600-NP12625.
- [10] Bélanger, J. J., Collier, K. E., Nisa, C. F., & Schumpe, B. M. (2021). Crimes of passion: When romantic obsession leads to abusive relationships. *Journal of personality*, 89(6), 1159-1175.
- [11] Bell, V., Wilkinson, S., Greco, M., Hendrie, C., Mills, B., & Deeley, Q. (2020). What is the functional/organic distinction actually doing in psychiatry and neurology?. *Wellcome Open Research*, 5.
- [12] Boyatzis, R. E. (1998). *Transforming qualitative information: Thematic analysis and code development*. sage.

- [13] Brem, M. J., Shorey, R. C., Ramsey, S. E., & Stuart, G. L. (2023). Randomized clinical trial of a brief alcohol intervention as an adjunct to batterer intervention for women arrested for domestic violence. *Psychosocial Intervention*, 32(2), 79-88.
- [14] Bricki, N. & Green, J. (2007). *A guide to using qualitative research methodology*. MedecinsSansFrontieres. Retrieved January 15, 2022 from <http://fieldresearch.msf.org/msf/handle/10144/84230>
- [15] Carey, D. (2021). 5. *Wives in Danger and Dangerous Women: Domestic and Female Violence*. In *I Ask for Justice* (pp. 153-190). University of Texas Press.
- [16] Campbell, A. (2021). What is learned helplessness, and how do you 'unlearn' it? <https://www.betterup.com/blog/learned-helplessness>. <https://www.betterup.com/blog/learned-helplessness>
- [17] Campbell, W. K., Foster, C. A., & Finkel, E. J. (2002). *Does self-love lead to love for others? A story of narcissistic game playing*. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 83(2), 340.
- [18] Castillo, M., Chan-Tayo, M. C., Celestino, A. B., Berse, K. B., & Quebral, D. J. A. (2021). *Gender Issues and Public Health Crisis Management: Philippine Local Governments' Response to Covid-19*. Available at SSRN 4041255.
- [19] Chen, J., Walters, M. L., Gilbert, L. K., & Patel, N. (2020). Sexual violence, stalking, and intimate partner violence by sexual orientation, United States. *Psychology of violence*, 10(1), 110.
- [20] Cheng, T. C., & Lo, C. C. (2021). *When child welfare caseworkers intervene, do women surviving IPV obtain recommended services?*. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 36(21-22), NP11446-NP11463.
- [21] Chiddaycha, M., & Wainipitapong, S. (2021). Mental health among Thai medical students: Preadmission evaluation and service utilization. *Health Science Reports*, 4(4), e416.
- [22] Chronister, K. M., Rao, K., Williams, L., Woodlee, K., Linville, D., Woods, C. R., ... & Vargas, K. (2022). *Contextual and cultural factors affecting network members' responses to Filipino survivors of partner abuse*. *Asian American Journal of Psychology*, 13(1), 83.
- [23] Chernet, A. G., & Cherie, K. T. (2020). *Prevalence of intimate partner violence against women and associated factors in Ethiopia*. *BMC women's health*, 20(1), 1-7.
- [24] Christensen, H. (2022). *Trauma Bonding in Intimate Partner Violence: A Depth Psychological Understanding* (Doctoral dissertation, Pacifica Graduate Institute).
- [25] Creswell, J.W. (2009). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. 3rd Edition. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, Inc., 2009.
- [26] Creswell, J.W. (2012). *Educational research. planning, conducting, and Evaluating: Quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Boston: MA: Pearson Education, Inc.
- [27] Crotty, M. (2006). *The foundations of social research. Meaning and perspective in the research process*. London: Sage. Data privacy act of 2012. Philippine Government Agencies Compliance.
- [28] Deb, A. (2021). Battered woman syndrome: prospect of situating it within criminal law in India. *BRICS Law Journal*, 8(4), 103-135.
- [29] De Wet, C. (2010). *The reasons for and the impact of principal-on-teache rbullying on the victims' private and professional lives*. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 26(7):1450-1459.
- [30] Dobash, R. P., & Dobash, R. E. (2004). Women's violence to men in intimate relationships: Working on a puzzle. *British journal of criminology*, 44(3), 324-349.
- [31] Dickerson-Amaya, N., & Coston, B. M. (2019). *Invisibility is not invincibility: the impact of intimate partner violence on gay, bisexual, and straight men's mental health*. *American Journal of men's health*, 13(3), 1557988319849734.
- [32] Elghossain, T., Bott, S., Akik, C., & Obermeyer, C. M. (2019). *Prevalence of intimate partner violence against women in the Arab world: a systematic review*. *BMC international health and human rights*, 19, 1-16.
- [33] Enaikele, M. D., & Adeoye, R. A. (2022). *Breaking Silence on Spousal Battery during Covid-19 Pandemic Era: A Case Study of Lagos State, Nigeria*. *KIU Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1), 175-185.

- [34] Estrellado, A. F., & Loh, J. (MI). (2019). *To Stay in or Leave an Abusive Relationship: Losses and Gains Experienced by Battered Filipino Women*. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 34(9), 1843–1863. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260516657912>
- [35] Festinger, L. (1957). *Social comparison theory*. *Selective Exposure Theory*, 16, 401.
- [36] Fleming, J. C., & Franklin, C. A. (2021). Predicting police endorsement of myths surrounding intimate partner violence. *Journal of family violence*, 36, 407-416
- [37] Gerstenberger, C., Stansfield, R., & Williams, K. R. (2019). *Intimate partnerviolence in same-sex relationships: An analysis of risk and Rearrest*. *Criminal justice and behavior*, 46(11), 1515-1527.
- [38] Gill, P., Stewart, K., Treasure, E., & Chadwick, B. (2008). *Methods of data collection in qualitative research: interviews and focus groups*. N.Y.; Macmillan Publishers Limited.
- [39] Given, L. M., & Saumure, K. (2008). *Trustworthiness*. SAGE New York: Publications, Inc.
- [40] Griffiths, E., & McLeod, B.(2008). Search engine as a diagnostic tool in difficult immunological and allergologic cases: is Google useful?. *Internal medicine journal*, 39(7), 459-464.
- [41] Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1982). *Establishing dependability and confirmability in naturalistic inquiry through an audit*. Paper presented at the Annual Meeting of the American Educational Research Association, New York, NY. Retrieved from <http://www.eric.ed.gov/PDFS/ED216019.pdf>
- [42] Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1989). *Fourth generation evaluation*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage
- [43] Gyamerah, A. O., Baguso, G., Santiago-Rodriguez, E., Sa'id, A., Arayasirikul, S., Lin, J., ... & Wesson, P. (2021). *Experiences and factors associated with transphobic hate crimes among transgender women in the San Francisco Bay Area: comparisons across race*. *BMC public health*, 21(1), 1-15.
- [44] Haag, H., Jones, D., Joseph, T., & Colantonio, A. (2022). *Battered and braininjured: traumatic brain injury among women survivors of intimate partner violence—a scoping review*. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 23(4), 1270-1287.
- [45] Hailes, H. P. (2023). *"They're Out to Take Away Your Sanity": An Ecological Investigation of Gaslighting in Intimate Partner Violence* (Doctoral dissertation, Boston College).
- [46] Han, X., & Wei, D. (2023). Advances in research on abused women in China: bibliometric analysis by citespace. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 24(2), 966-980.
- [47] Hancock B., Ockleford, E., & Windridge, K. (2007). *An introduction to qualitative research*. The NIHRRDSEM/YH.
- [48] Haque, M. A., Choudhury, N., Ahmed, S. T., Farzana, F. D., Ali, M., Rahman, S. S., ... & Ahmed, T. (2022). *Factors associated with domestic violence in rural Bangladesh*. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 37(3-4), 1248-1269.
- [49] Hennink, M., & Kaiser, B. N. (2022). Sample sizes for saturation in qualitative research: A systematic review of empirical tests. *Social science & medicine*, 292, 114523.
- [50] Heydari, A., Teymoori, A., & Trappes, R. (2021). *Honor killing as a dark side of modernity: Prevalence, common discourses, and a critical view*. *Social Science Information*, 0539018421994777.
- [51] Holmes, S. C., Maxwell, C. D., Cattaneo, L. B., Bellucci, B. A., & Sullivan, T. P. (2022). Criminal Protection orders among women victims of intimate Partner violence: Women's Experiences of Court decisions, processes, and their willingness to Engage with the system in the future. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 37(17-18), NP16253-NP16276.
- [52] Hui, V., & Constantino, R. E. (2021). *The association between life satisfaction, emotional support, and perceived health among women who experienced intimate Partner violence (IPV)–2007 behavioral risk factor surveillancesystem*. *BMC public health*, 21(1), 1-8.
- [53] Johnson, J. L., Adkins, D., & Chauvin, S. (2020). A review of the quality indicators of rigor in qualitative research. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 84(1).

- [54] Jones, Alexandra, and Arlene Vetere. 2017. 'You just deal with it. You have to when you've got a child': A narrative analysis of mothers' accounts of how they coped, both during an abusive relationship and after leaving. *Clinical Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 22: 74–89.
- [55] Joseph, J., & Canlas, R. P. (2023). Efficacy of Self-supportive Intervention Program on Post-traumatic Stress Disorder and Quality of life among Battered Wives in Madhya Pradesh, India. *Indian Journal of Positive Psychology*, 14(1).
- [56] Kassas, S., Abdelnour, N., & Makhoul, J. (2022). "Hitting as Light as Feathers": Religious Leaders' Voices on Domestic Violence. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 37(3-4), 1270-1291.
- [57] Kelly, L. C., Spencer, C. M., Keilholtz, B., McAllister, P., & Stith, S. M. (2022). Is separate the new equal? A meta-analytic review of correlates of intimate partner violence victimization for black and white women in the united states. *Family Process*.
- [58] Letourneau, N., Luis, M. A., Kurbatfinski, S., Ferrara, H. J., Pohl, C., Marabotti, F., & Hayden, K. A. (2022). COVID-19 and family violence: a rapid review of literature published up to 1 year after the pandemic declaration. *EClinicalMedicine*, 53.
- [59] Lochmiller, C. R., & Lester, J. N. (2016). *An Introduction to educational research connecting methods to practice*. Retrieved from <https://us.sagepub.com/en-us/nam/an-introduction-to-educational-research/book243411SAGEPublications>
- [60] Lucas, A. S. (2018). *Violence against women. Current procedural needs, with special reference to Panamá*. *Journal of Modern Science*, 38(3), 111–132.
- [61] Lux, G., & Gill, S. (2021). *Identifying coercive control in Canadian family law: A required analysis in determining the best interests of the child*. *Family courtreview*, 59(4), 810-827.
- [62] Lysova, A., & Dim, E. E. (2022). *Severity of victimization and formal help seeking among men who experienced intimate partner violence in their ongoing relationships*. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 37(3-4), 1404-1429.
- [63] Mack, N., Woodsong, C., MacQueen, K.M., Guest, G., & Namey, E. (2005). *Qualitative research methods: a data collector's field guide*. Retrieved from <http://www.fhi360.org> Accessed
- [64] Macalalad, A. K. S. (2020). *Hunger for Justiciability and Judicial Exigibility: Claiming the Human Rights to Adequate Food before Philippine Courts*. *Phil. LJ*, 93, 140.
- [65] Makhanya, M. T. B. (2022). Feminist Approach to the Theology of Sin and Forgiveness in Intimate Partner Violence Within Marriage in the Anglican Church of Southern Africa. *Pharos Journal of Theology*, 103(2).
- [66] March, E., Kay, C. S., Dinić, B. M., Wagstaff, D., Grabovac, B., & Jonason, P. K. (2023). "It's All in Your Head": Personality Traits and Gaslighting Tactics in Intimate Relationships. *Journal of Family Violence*, 1-10.
- [67] Martins, S. (2020). *Sylvia Plath: Journey to The Colossus* (Doctoral dissertation, Mississippi College).
- [68] Matheson, F. I., Daoud, N., Hamilton-Wright, S., Borenstein, H., Pedersen, C., & O'Campo, P. (2015). Where did she go? The transformation of self-esteem, self-identity, and mental well-being among women who have experienced intimate partner violence. *Women's health issues*, 25(5), 561-569.
- [69] May, A. (2022). Janie's Got a Gun (and No Other Option): The Harsh Reality for Battered Women Claiming Duress in Federal Court. *Tex. Tech L. Rev.*, 55, 249.
- [70] McLeod, D. A., Ozturk, B., Butler-King, R. L., & Peek, H. (2023). Male survivors of domestic violence, challenges in cultural response, and impact on identity and help-seeking behaviors: a systematic review. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 15248380231177318.
- [71] Messing, J. T., AbiNader, M. A., Pizarro, J. M., Campbell, J. C., Brown, M. L., & Pelletier, K. R. (2021). The Arizona intimate partner homicide (AZIPH) study: A step toward updating and expanding risk factors for intimate partner homicide. *Journal of family violence*, 36, 563-572.
- [72] Meyer, S. R., Lasater, M. E., & Garcia-Moreno, C. (2020). *Violence against older women: A systematic review of qualitative literature*. *PloS one*, 15(9), e0239560.

- [73] Mike, M. (2011). *Credibility of research results*. Retrieved from <http://credibility-rsmet.blogspot.com/2011/11/ensuring-credibility-of-qualitative.html>
- [74] Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: A sourcebook of new methods* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage
- [75] Mohan, S., & Hassan, A. (2022). Reading of Intertextuality in the Notions of Domestic Violence in Select Texts with Reference to Meena Kandasamy's *When I Hit You*. *World Journal of English Language*, 12(2).
- [76] Mohd Arifin, S. R. (2018). *Ethical Considerations in Qualitative Study*. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CARE SCHOLARS*, 1(2), 30–33. <https://doi.org/10.31436/ijcs.v1i2.82>
- [77] Morada, N. M. (2019). *ASEAN regionalism and capacity-building for atrocities prevention: Challenges and prospects. Implementing the Responsibility to Protect*, 89-108.
- [78] Moustakas, C. (1994). *Phenomenological research methods*. Thousand Oaks, Calif.; London, Sage
- [79] Mojahed, A., Alaidarous, N., Shabta, H., Hegewald, J., & Garthus-Niegel, S. (2022). *Intimate partner violence against women in the Arab countries: a systematic review of risk factors*. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 23(2), 390-407.
- [80] Mondal, D., & Paul, P. (2021). *Associations of power relations, wife-beating attitudes, and controlling behavior of husband with domestic violence against women in India: Insights from the National Family Health Survey–4*. *Violence against women*, 27(14), 2530-2551.
- [81] Morgan, D. L. (1998). *Practical strategies for combining qualitative and quantitative methods: Applications to health research*. *Qualitative health research*, 8(3), 362-376.
- [82] Morrow, S. L. (2005). *Quality and trustworthiness in qualitative research in counseling psychology*. *Journal of counseling psychology*, 52(2), 250.
- [83] Munir, M. M., Munir, M. H., & Rubaca, U. (2021). *The Shadow Pandemic: Violence against Women in Pakistan during COVID-19 Lockdown*. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 22(5), 229-248.
- [84] Murphy, E. C., Segura, E. R., Lake, J. E., Huerta, L., Perez-Brumer, A. G., Mayer, K. H., ... & Clark, J. L. (2020). *Intimate partner violence against transgender women: prevalence and correlates in Lima, Peru (2016–2018)*. *AIDS and Behavior*, 24, 1743-1751.
- [85] Namey, G., Guest, G., Thairu, L. & Johnson, L. (2007). *Data reduction techniques for large qualitative data sets*. Retrieved March 1, 2022 from www.stanford.edu/~thairu/07_184.Guest.1sts.pdf
- [86] Nelson, P. (2021). *Global Development and Human Rights: The Sustainable Development Goals and Beyond*. University of Toronto Press.
- [87] Nigam, S. (2016). *Battered Women Syndrome: Applying this Legal Doctrine in the Indian Context*. Available at SSRN 2819322.
- [88] Notko, M., Husso, M., Piippo, S., Fagerlund, M., & Houtsonen, J. (2022). *Intervening in domestic violence: interprofessional collaboration among social and health care professionals and the police*. *Journal of interprofessional care*, 36(1), 15-23.
- [89] Nuttman-Shwartz, O., & Regev, I. (2018). *Life in a continuous traumatic situation: perspective of the older population*. *Ageing & Society*, 38(5), 954-973.
- [90] Olsson, H., & Bergman, A. (2022). *From silence to recognition: Swedish social services and the handling of honor-based violence*. *European journal of social work*, 25(2), 198-209.
- [91] Ozuem, W., Willis, M., & Howell, K. (2022). *Thematic analysis without paradox: sensemaking and context*. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 25(1), 143-157.
- [92] Panjaphothiwat, N., Tamornpark, R., Apidechkul, T., Seeprasert, P., Singkhorn, O., Upala, P., ... & Sunsern, R. (2021). *Factors associated with domestic violence in the Lahu hill tribe of northern Thailand: A cross-sectional study*. *Plos one*, 16(3), e0248587.

- [93] Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). *Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research*. Retrieved from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/24193818>.
- [94] Patmisari, E., & McLaren, H. (2022). Australian trends in academic literature concerned with family and domestic violence perpetrators: a bibliometric literature review. *Trauma, Violence, & Abuse*, 15248380221113786.
- [95] Patton, M. Q. (1990). *Qualitative evaluation and research methods (2nded.)*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage Publications.
- [96] Patton, M. Q. (2015). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods*. <http://johnljerz.com/superduper/tlxdownloadsiteWEBSITEII/id384.html>
- [97] Paul, K. (2006). Analyzing qualitative data. In *Qualitative Analysis Handout* (pp. 97-153). Retrieved April 14, 2022 from <http://www.scribd.com/doc/187185840/Qualitative-Analysis-Handout>
- [98] Peterman, A., Potts, A., O'Donnell, M., Thompson, K., Shah, N., Oertelt-Prigione, S., & Van Gelder, N. (2020). *Pandemics and violence against women and children* (Vol. 528, pp. 1-45). Washington, DC: Center for Global Development.
- [99] Pereda, N., & Díaz-Faes, D. A. (2020). Family violence against children in the wake of COVID-19 pandemic: a review of current perspectives and risk factors. *Child and adolescent psychiatry and mental health*, 14(1), 1-7.
- [100] Province, S. (2021). *Mainstreaming Co-Management Strategies on PKKK's Women-Led Community-Based Gender Based Violence (GBV) Watch Group in Barangay Palaypay, Municipality of Basesy.R.A. 9262. Anti-Violence Against Women and their Children*
- [101] Rabaan, H., Young, A. L., & Dombrowski, L. (2021). *Daughters of men: Saudi women's sociotechnical agency practices in addressing domestic abuse*. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 4(CSCW3), 1-31.
- [102] Radell, M. L., Abo Hamza, E. G., Daghustani, W. H., Perveen, A., & Moustafa, A. A. (2021). The impact of different types of abuse on depression. *Depression research and treatment*, 2021.
- [103] Ramsey, C.J. (2010). *Teacher's experiences with student bullying in five rural middle schools*. Unpublished dissertation, Western Carolina University, Cullowhee, NC. Retrieved October 15, 2022 from <http://www.ramseycasestudyonstudentbullying.pdf>
- [104] Rai, A., Choi, Y. J., Yoshihama, M., & Dabby, C. (2022). *Help-seeking among battered immigrant Filipina, Indian, and Pakistani women in the United States: Perceived barriers and helpful responses*. *Violence and victims*, 36(6), 823-838.
- [105] Rai, A., & Choi, Y. J. (2022). Domestic violence victimization among south Asian immigrant men and women in the United States. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 37(17-18), NP15532-NP15567.
- [106] Raveesh, B. N., Rai, S., Kaur, D., Bandyopadhyay, D., Gautam, A., Shetty, J., & Parmar, J. M. (2022). *Domestic Violence Current Legal Status: Psychiatric Evaluation of Victims and Offenders*. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 64(Suppl 1), S134-S145
- [107] Realin, R. A. P. (2019). Justice across Borders: The State Obligation of the Philippines to Recognize and Enforce Foreign Judgments Awarding Reparation to Victims of Gross Human Rights Violations Committed within Philippine Jurisdiction. *U. Asia & Pacific LJ*, 2, 100.
- [108] Rebbe, R., Lyons, V. H., Webster, D., & Putnam-Hornstein, E. (2021). Domestic violence alleged in California child maltreatment reports during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of family violence*, 1-8.
- [109] Reckenwald, A., & Parker, K. (2012). *Understanding the change in male and female intimate partner homicide over time: A policy and theory-relevant investigation*. *Feminist Criminology*, 7, 167-195.
- [110] Renzetti, C. M., Lynch, K. R., Jewell, J. A., Wasarhaley, N. E., & Golding, J. M. (2020). *Great expectations: The impact of participant gender, defendant desirability, and date cost on attributions of a date rape victim and defendant*. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 35(17-18), 3437-3461.

- [111] Riddell, T., Ford-Gilboe, M., & Leipert, B. (2009). *Strategies use by rural women to stop, avoid or escape from intimate partner violence*. *Health Care for Women International*, 30, 134-159. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07399330802523774>
- [112] Roulston, K. (2001). *Data analysis and theorizing as ideology*. *Qualitative research*, 1(3), 279-302.
- [113] Rutherford, S., Barkema, P., Tso, I. F., Sripada, C., Beckmann, C. F., Ruhe, H. G., & Marquand, A. F. (2023). Evidence for embracing normative modeling. *Elife*, 12, e85082.
- [114] Sabarre, J., Villareal, P. L. H., & Arcinas, M. (2021). *Filipino Adolescents' Experiences of Abusive Parent-Child Relationship in Low Socioeconomic Status Families*. *Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Studies*, 3(4), 06-18.
- [115] Sabri, B., Rai, A., & Rameshkumar, A. (2022). Violence against women in India: an analysis of correlates of domestic violence and barriers and facilitators of access to resources for support. *Journal of Evidence-Based Social Work*, 19(6), 700-729.
- [116] Sáez, G., López-Nuñez, C., Carlos-Vivas, J., Barrios-Fernandez, S., Rojo-Ramos, J., Adsuar, J. C., & Collado-Mateo, D. (2021). A multicomponent program to improve self-concept and self-esteem among intimate partner violence victims: A study protocol for a randomized controlled pilot trial. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(9), 4930.
- [117] Sani, A. I., & Pereira, D. (2020). *Mothers as Victims of Intimate Partner Violence: The Decision to Leave or Stay and Resilience-Oriented Intervention*. *Social Sciences*, 9(10), 174. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci9100174>
- [118] Sangeetha, J., Mohan, S., Hariharasudan, A., & Nawaz, N. (2022). *Strategic analysis of intimate partner violence (IPV) and cycle of violence in the autobiographical text—When I Hit You*. *Heliyon*, 8(6), e09734.
- [119] Sardinha, L., Maheu-Giroux, M., Stöckl, H., Meyer, S. R., & García-Moreno, C. (2022). *Global, regional, and national prevalence estimates of physical or sexual, or both, intimate partner violence against women in 2018*. *The Lancet*, 399(10327), 803-813.
- [120] Shah, P. K., & Jacob, J. (2023). *Beyond abortion decriminalization: human rights perspectives on the role of law in creating enabling environments for abortion access*. In *Research Handbook on International Abortion Law* (pp. 343-373). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- [121] Seligman, M. E. (1975). *Depression and learned helplessness in man*. *Journal of abnormal psychology*, 84(3), 228.
- [122] Subiani, S. A. (2023). Saudi Women's Abuse and Help-Seeking Experiences: A Qualitative Thematic Analysis.
- [123] Sun, I. Y., Wu, Y., Wang, X., & Xue, J. (2022). Officer and organizational correlates with police interventions in domestic violence in China. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 37(11-12), NP8325-NP8349.
- [124] Susmitha B. (2016). *Domestic Violence: Causes, Impact and Remedial Measures*. *Social Change*, 46(4), 602-610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049085716666636>
- [125] Suter, N. (2012). *Introduction to educational research: a critical thinking approach*, 2nd Ed. Sage Publications, Inc. Retrieved June 4, 2022 from <http://www.sagepub.com/books/Book235696/toc>
- [126] Tan, V. T. (2018). *Sleeping with my abuser: A qualitative study on the development of transferred aggression expression among battered women*. *IAFOR Journal of Psychology & the Behavioral Sciences*, 4(1).
- [127] Vakil, M. (2020). *Battered Woman Syndrome as a Legal Defence in Cases of Spousal Homicide: An Indian Perspective*. *Supremo Amicus*, 18, 526.
- [128] Valenzuela-Vela, L., & Alcázar-Campos, A. (2020). Gendered carceral logics in social work: The blurred boundaries in gender equality policies for imprisoned and battered women in Spain. *Affilia*, 35(1), 73-88.
- [129] Van Manen, M. (1990). *Beyond assumptions: Shifting the limits of action research*. *Theory into practice*, 29(3), 152-157.
- [130] Van Manen, M. (2014). *Phenomenology of practice: Meaning-giving methods in phenomenological research and writing*. Taylor & Francis.

- [131] VictimSupportUK (2021). *Promoting the psychological well-being of healthcare providers facing the burden of adverse events: a systematic review of second victim support resources*. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 18(10), 5080.
- [132] Walker, A., Lyall, K., Silva, D., Craigie, G., Mayshak, R., Costa, B., ... & Bentley, A. (2020). *Male victims of female-perpetrated intimate partner violence, help-seeking, and reporting behaviors: A qualitative study*. *Psychology of Men & Masculinities*, 21(2), 213.
- [133] Wild, K., Young, F., de Araujo, G., Fernandes, A., Gomes, L., Kelly, L., & Taft, A. (2022). Healthcare responses to gender-based violence in Timor-Leste: women want empathy, information and safety from an integrated support system. *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 37(23-24), NP22175-NP22198.
- [134] Woerner, J., Sullivan, T. P., Cattaneo, L. B., Backes, B. L., & Bellucci, B. (2023). Criminal Orders of Protection for Survivors of Intimate Partner Violence, Future System Engagement, and Well-Being: Understanding the Importance of Prior Abusive Relationships. *Victims & Offenders*, 1-20.
- [135] World Health Organization. (2016). *Violence Against Women: Intimate Partner and Sexual Violence Against Women*. Retrieved from <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs239/en/>
- [136] Xue, J., Chen, J., Chen, C., Hu, R., & Zhu, T. (2020). *The hidden pandemic of family violence during COVID-19: unsupervised learning of tweets*. *Journal of medical Internet research*, 22(11), e24361.
- [137] Yin, R. (2003). *Applications of Case Study Research*. Second Edition, Applied Social Research Methods Series. Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks, CA.
- [138] Zacarias, A. E. Macassa, G., & Soares, J. J. F. (2012). *Women as perpetrators of IPV: The experience of Mozambique*. *Journal of Aggression, Conflict and Peace Research*, 4, 5- 27 <https://doi.org/10.1108/17596591211192966>
- [139] Zepinic, V. (2021). Battered women syndrome: a headache for medicine and law. *Psychology*, 12(6), 843-871.
- [140] Zepinic, V. (2023). *Battered Woman Syndrome: The Iceberg of Domestic Violence*. *Beijing Law Review*, 14(1), 143-161.
- [141] Zuazo, S. S. (2022). *An examination of three emerging interventions and proposed best practices to treat Latina women who have experienced intimate partner violence* (Doctoral dissertation, Alliant International University).